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MUSCULAR POWER AS A FUNCTION OF LOAD IN ELDERLY WOMEN

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1. Introduction

Aging has been associated with a decrease in the ability to perform daily tasks (Reid and Fielding, 2012). This decrease in functional performance is due to a reduction of the muscle strength but also of the muscle power. A lower capacity of developing force and power results in impaired performance, particularly in activities where intense and rapid movements are essential as, for example, avoiding oncoming traffic or counter-acting a fall.

It has been shown that increasing muscle power in older adults results in a functional improvement and reduces the incidence of disability (Pereira et al. 2012). To improve muscular power, trainings that maximize power output are indicated (Kawamori and Haff, 2004).

Muscular power can be assessed using isokinetic or iso-inertial dynamometry. Even if isokinetic testing remains one of the more popular methods for power assessment, it may not be appropriate to assess the ability to perform daily tasks (Jane, 1995). Indeed, the fixed velocity of movement utilized during isokinetic testing is not characteristic of most daily activities. Instead, iso-inertial testing approximates more closely functional movements, which are characterized by accelerations of a constant mass.

In this study, we have measured the average power during upper and lower body exercises using an iso-inertial method in older women. The aim is (1) to evaluate the strength and power in aging women and (2) to determine the load (or range of loads) that maximizes the mechanical power output.

2. Methods

Thirty-four older women, 60-81 year of age (age: 65.7 ± 4.8 years; height: 1.47 ± 0.04 m; body mass: 68.2 ± 12.4 kg; mean \pm SD) participated to this study. Informed consent was obtained. Subjects were not suffering from any pathology that could severely disrupt the full range of movement. Project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Universidad Finis Terrae.

Subjects were first familiarized with the testing procedures and equipment. Then during a second session, maximal strength and power were measured: first the bench press test (*BP*) and then the leg press test (*LP*), with 1-hour rest between tests. *BP* exercises were performed on a Smith Machine model S3-020 and *LP* exercises on a leg press model S3-022 (R2sport, Forest Park, Illinois, USA).

Subjects started from a fully extended elbow/knee position, then they were lowering the bar, until the elbow/knee reached an angle of 90°. Then, subjects performed the concentric contraction of the extensor muscles as fast as possible until reaching full elbow/knee extension. All subjects started with an empty bar (mass: 11 kg for *BP* and 40 kg for *LP*), thereafter the load was progressively increased by adding masses on the bar (2.5-5 kg for *BP* or 10-25 kg for *LP*, depending on the perceived exertion). The load increments were performed until the subject was unable to reach the full extension of the lower/upper limb. A 2 min rest was given between each trial. The full extension with the highest load was determined as *IRM-BP/LP*.

Results were grouped in classes of 10% of *IRM*. The data were compared using one-way ANOVA and Bonferoni post-hoc comparisons.

3. Results

Fig. 1 Average power (filled circles) and velocity (open circles) as a function of the load (expressed as a percentage of the *IRM*) during an extension movement of the upper limbs (upper panel) and of the lower limb (lower panel). Each point is the average of all the data obtained within a 10% load class. Bars represent ± 1 SD. Linear (interrupted line) and polynomial (continuous line) curve fit are computed through all the data (KGraph 4.5). The stars indicate the classes where the power is significantly lower.

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The weight-specific *IRM-BP* is $0.41 \pm 0.11 BW$ (mean \pm SD, *BW*: Body Weight) and the *IRM-LP* is $2.15 \pm 0.54 BW$. We did not find a significant correlation between age and *IRM-BP* ($r = -0.23$, $P > 0.08$), whereas *IRM-LP* decreased significantly with age ($r = -0.59$, $P < 0.001$).

Both in *BP* and *LP*, the average speed of movement decreases linearly when the load increases (Fig. 1), from 0.6 m s^{-1} with a load of 20% of *IRM*, to 0.2 m s^{-1} for a load corresponding to *IRM*.

The power developed during the extension of the upper and the lower limbs presents an inverted U-shape curve (Fig. 1) with a maximal power output for a load of ~60% of *IRM*.

However, in *BP* (upper panel), the average power output was not significantly different across the load-range of 40-90% of *IRM* ($P > 0.05$). Whereas for loads of 20%, 30% of *IRM* and of *IRM*, the average power output was significantly lower ($P < 0.001$). In *LP*, the average power output was not significantly different across the load-range of 40-80% of *IRM* ($P > 0.05$). For load $< 40\%$ and $> 80\%$ of *IRM*, the power was significantly lower ($P < 0.001$).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

For *BP*, the weight-specific average *IRM* measured on elderly Chilean women (*CW*: $0.41 \pm 0.11 BW$) are in agreement with the norms of the American College of Sports Medicine (*ACSM*: $0.45 \pm 0.28 BW$), but are higher than the values of the Women's Exercise Research Center (*WERC*: $0.30 \pm 0.12 BW$) (Brown and Miller, 1998). For *LP*, our subjects are lifting a weight put on a rail inclined at 45° , whereas in the two other studies, the subjects are using a sitting leg press and lift the weight vertically. For comparison, our values should be multiplied by $\sin 45^\circ$. In this case, *CW*: $1.52 \pm 0.39 BW$ - *ACSM*: $1.03 \pm 0.37 BW$ - *WERC*: $1.16 \pm 0.37 BW$. Note that both in *BP* and *LP*, the standard deviations are rather important, showing the great dispersion of the muscular force observed in elderly women.

In our study, the mean power was maximized for a load of 60-65% *IRM* during *BP* and *LP* exercises, although mean power output was not significantly different across the load ranges of 40-90% *IRM* for *BP* and 40-80% *IRM* for *LP*. These results are in concordance with the study of de Vos et al. (2005).

Our results suggest that there is no optimal load to develop muscle power in older women, but rather a range of loads that can be used to optimize the development of muscle power. Several studies have analysed the influence of the velocity component of muscle power on functional performance and have demonstrated that high velocity power training are the most efficient to improve muscle power in older adults (Henwood et al. 2008).

The findings described here above suggest that even if power output is similar at certain points along the power curve, the different velocities at which power is obtained could be a key factor in functional responses. Therefore, we recommend

peak muscle power training with loads of 40-50% *IRM*, rather than 70-80% *IRM*.

Furthermore, higher leg press contraction velocity was associated with better performance in maintaining balance (Marsh et al. 2009), better mobility and better walking performance, in the elderly population (Sayers et al. 2005).

Note that certain tasks may require power with a great force rather than power with a great velocity (e.g. getting up from a chair). Enhancing muscle strength remains thus an important component of functional training programs. Besides, development of muscular strength is an important element in the long-term development of maximal muscular power (Zamparo et al. 2002).

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